

ROLE OF E-RESOURCES IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

New technologies have always been of interest for libraries both for the potential of increasing the quality of service and for improving efficiency of operations. At present libraries of all kinds whether public, research academic or special libraries are overwhelmingly looking forward to adopt new technologies mostly use of e-resources due to its potential for cost savings in operations and the management of collections and Patrons. E- Resources are digital objects containing electronic representation of books, journals and other form of reading materials and they are converted into a digitized form in order to be read by a computer.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern academic libraries, a conglomeration of printed books and journals as well as electronic resources (e- resources) where both forms of documents can be stored, retrieved and delivered *as* and when required. The library should have good number of Resources for teaching, learning and Research work. E- Resources offer creative possibilities for expanding access as well as changing learning, teaching and research work. Contents of E-Resources can be accessible, at any place regardless of time, to be read at personal computers. E-books would never to go out of print, and new editions can be easily created.

2. LIBRARY AUTOMATION

The main purpose of library automation is to improve the efficiency of library and to provide optimum user services. The automated library system is capable of handling large volumes of documents and of providing timely and effective information services to faculty, research scholars and students in achieving their goals.

include journal articles, newspapers articles, books reviews and conference proceedings, etc. e-databases usually updated on a daily, weekly, monthly or quarterly basis. Full text databases contain the whole content of an article such as citation information, text, illustrations, diagrams and tables. Bibliographic databases only contain citation information of an article, such as author name, journal title, publication date and page numbers.

3.1 E- Books

An electronic book is a text and image-based publication in digital form produced on published by and readable on computers, other digital devices. E-books are usually read on dedicated hardware devices known as e-Readers or e-book devices. Personal computers and some cell phones can also be used to read e-books. E-books are preferred by the users for their features like portability, upgradeability, note making, citation, changeable font size, links to other relevant sites, searching etc. E-books can be transferred from library catalogue to users e-book readers for a fixed loan period and after which it is automatically taken back. An e-book can be offered indefinitely without ever going “out of print”.

3.2 E-Journals

An electronic journal, as its name implies is a serial containing research papers review articles, scholarly communication, issued periodically in electronic form, by using computer. E-journals may be defined very broadly as any journals, magazine, e-zine, webzine, newsletters or any type of electronic serial publication, which is available over the internet. In the electronic environment teaching, learning and research are being supported by e-journals as new powerful tools. E-journals have an impact not only on libraries but on authors and publishers too. Correct and timely information is a key to sound decisions. Hence, now-a-days majority of the users expect more relevant, up to-date and timely information from modern library and information centers. For these purposes library and information centers need accessibility to a variety of information resources and in various formats. Information from journals can easily, quickly, pin-pointedly and remotely be retrieved, provided the journals are available in electronic format

